

Determination of some Substituted Hydroxychalcones in Non-aqueous Medium by Enthalpimetric, Conductometric and Potentiometric Titrations

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2'-Hydroxy-5'-methylchalcone (HMC), 2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl-4-methoxychalcone (HMMOC) and 2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl-3,4-methylenedioxychalcone (HMMDOC) have been used for analytical studies of metal complexes¹ and antimicrobial activities². Considering its analytical and biocidal importance, it was thought worthwhile to develop a suitable method for determination of HMC, HMMOC and HMMDOC in microquantities.

In continuation of our earlier work on the titrimetric determination of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-dibenzoylmethane³ and 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl-dibenzoylmethane⁴ in non-aqueous medium, the present work was undertaken to determine HMC, HMMOC and HMMDOC by enthalpimetric, conductometric and potentiometric methods, and also to determine the optimum conditions for their quantitative estimations.

Results and Discussion

t-Bu₄NOH and alcoholic KOH were used for enthalpimetric, conductometric and potentiometric titrations. Results show that alcoholic KOH gives the best results for all the three methods, hence it was used as a titrant for further investigation.

From the stock solution of HMC containing 2.380 mg ml⁻¹ of the compound, different volumes (1 to 20 ml) were diluted to 20 ml by acetone, and 2 ml of each of these solutions was titrated against alcoholic KOH enthalpimetrically, con-

ductometrically and potentiometrically. Similar titrations were performed for HMMOC and HMMDOC. Results (Table 1) reveal that enthalpimetric titrations are suitable for estimation of chalcones in lower concentrations (1.0–14.0 mg). For higher concentration, percentage error increases and becomes negative indicating incomplete reaction. Thus, it becomes necessary to use larger volumes of solvent to get reliable results. However, the method is much quicker than the conductometric and potentiometric titrations and hence is recommended for quicker determination of chalcones. Comparison of the results (Table 1) shows that in conductometric titration with alcoholic KOH the concentration range was 0.5–23.0 mg for HMC, 0.6–21.0 mg for HMMOC and 0.7–26.0 mg for HMMDOC with an accuracy of $\pm 2\%$.

Potentiometric titration shows the concentration range of 0.5–24.0 mg for HMC, 0.6–27.0 mg for HMMOC and 0.7–28.0 mg for HMMDOC with the same accuracy under the experimental conditions. Potentiometric titrations are therefore recommended for the estimation of chalcones.

Experimental

Two titrants, tetra-n-butylammonium hydroxide (t-Bu₄NOH) and potassium hydroxide in isopropanol (alcoholic KOH) were prepared and preserved as described earlier³.

TABLE I—TITRATIONS OF SUBSTITUTED HYDROXYCHALCONES

Compd.	Weight taken mg	Enthalpimetric		Conductometric		Potentiometric	
		Wt. found mg	% Error	Wt. found mg	% Error	Wt. found mg	% Error
HMC	0.595	0.576	-3.1	0.580	-2.5	0.604	+1.4
	1.190	1.160	-2.5	1.171	-1.5	1.208	+1.5
	2.380	2.335	-1.9	2.415	+1.4	2.342	-1.5
	4.760	4.689	-1.5	4.779	+0.3	4.781	+0.4
	7.140	7.122	-0.2	7.215	+1.0	7.173	+0.4
	9.520	9.559	+0.4	9.604	+0.8	9.616	+1.0
	11.900	11.996	+0.8	11.712	-1.5	11.769	-1.1
	14.280	14.008	-1.9	14.037	-1.7	14.103	-1.2
	16.660	16.211	-2.7	16.255	-2.4	16.444	-1.3
	19.040	18.489	-2.9	18.755	-1.5	19.123	+0.4
	21.420	20.692	-3.4	21.035	-1.7	21.549	-0.6
	23.801	22.682	-4.7	23.372	-1.8	23.900	+0.4
	HMMOC	0.670	0.689	+2.9	0.659	-1.5	0.667
1.340		1.361	+1.5	1.322	-1.3	1.332	-0.5
2.680		2.692	+0.4	2.637	-1.5	2.664	-0.5
5.360		5.384	+0.4	5.444	+1.5	5.339	-0.4
8.041		8.146	+1.3	7.945	-1.2	7.977	-0.8
10.723		10.773	+0.5	10.583	-1.3	10.654	-0.6
13.406		13.205	-1.5	13.232	-1.3	13.299	-0.8
16.092		15.787	-1.9	15.867	-1.4	15.947	-0.9
18.773		18.341	-2.3	18.472	-1.6	18.566	-1.1
21.453		20.788	-3.1	21.067	-1.8	21.239	-1.0
24.134		23.120	-4.2	23.627	-2.1	23.820	-1.3
26.814		25.446	-5.1	26.197	-2.3	26.412	-1.5
HMMDOC		0.705	0.693	-2.2	0.717	+1.6	0.701
	1.410	1.383	-1.9	1.427	+1.2	1.416	+0.2
	2.820	2.772	-1.6	2.867	+1.6	2.800	+0.7
	5.640	5.730	+1.6	5.555	-1.5	5.637	-0.1
	8.460	8.426	-0.4	8.367	-1.1	8.438	-0.2
	11.280	11.223	-0.5	11.190	-0.8	11.258	-0.2
	14.100	13.931	-1.2	13.903	-1.4	13.973	-0.9
	16.920	16.616	-1.8	16.683	-1.4	16.734	-1.1
	19.740	19.346	-2.0	19.405	-1.7	19.484	-1.3
	22.560	21.861	-3.1	22.199	-1.6	22.900	-1.2
	25.380	24.340	-4.1	25.000	-1.5	25.152	-0.9
	28.200	26.734	-5.2	27.756	-1.5	28.029	-0.6

The chalcones HMC, HMMOC and HMMDOC were prepared by known methods and the purity of the compound was checked by tlc and also by their m.ps. Melting points and molecular weights of HMC, HMMOC, HMMDOC were found to be 99° and 238, 98° and 268 and 112° and 282 respectively.

All solvents were of A.R. grade and made anhydrous by standard methods⁵.

A Systronics 304 instrument was used for conductometric titration. The potential measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ with a Systronics 335 pH meter. Glass electrode was

NOTE

used as reference electrode and antimony/antimony oxide electrode as indicator electrode.

All titration were carried in nitrogen atmosphere in triplicate in acetone medium. Methods for enthalpimetric, conductometric and potentiometric titrations were necessarily the same as reported earlier³. End-points were determined graphically.

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